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ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

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Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report –
part 1 | Date 29-dec-2023

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

E³UDRES² – Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

GnA – General Assembly

HEIs – Higher education institutions

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is a collaborative endeavor aimed at refining a comprehensive joint research and innovation strategy, alongside a unified agenda. The overarching ambition is to catalyze the transformation of E³UDRES² into a distinguished European multi-institutional Research and Innovation Hub specializing in Smart and Sustainable Regions.

This deliverable encapsulates the achievements and strategic milestones attained during the initial reporting period (M1-M15) of the project. The primary focus has been on the dynamic interplay of dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategies outlined in the D1.2 – Project Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan.

Aligned with the outlined objectives in the Description of Action (DoA), section 2.2 of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Grant Agreement, the strategies elucidated here exemplify a deliberate and cohesive approach. The clarity of alignment is manifested through a detailed definition of target audiences, communication areas and dimensions, objectives, messages, channels, types of activities, and a comprehensive timeline spanning the 36-month duration of the project. The definition of these aspects took shape in “D1.2 – Project communication and dissemination plan”.

As we go through this landscape, the strategic sequencing of our communication initiatives serves as a precursor to the forthcoming phases of comprehensive dissemination and exploitation. This intentional progression ensures that insights, innovations, and accomplishments cultivated during the initial project phase are effectively translated into tangible outcomes and benefits for stakeholders, contributing to the realization of the project's overarching objectives.

1. Tasks

Task T.1.4 Project communication dissemination and exploitation plan (IPS, all participants) M1-M6

Task leader: IPS

Contributors: All partners

This task was completed and submitted by the end of month 6 as scheduled, resulting from the deliverable “D1.2 Project communication and dissemination plan”. In this task, the communication dissemination and exploitation activities are developed. The activities developed and presented below followed what is planned in this deliverable.

2. Activities

In addition to carrying out Task T1.4., the only task related to communication, dissemination and exploitation, E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators has been carrying out a set of communication, dissemination activities. Emphasizing the importance of making tangible use of project results, our activities in the first phase of the project have focused predominantly on communication, with a supplementary focus on dissemination.

At the beginning of the project, after the definition of the communication, dissemination and exploitation targets and goal (“D1.2 – Project communication and dissemination plan”), the development of its visual identity was initiated, including the development of the logo and the Brand Book with the standards manual associated with the use of the project’s logo and visual identity. The manual defines rules, measures, typography and colours. Templates for presentations, minutes, deliverables, newsletter, reports and visual graphics to social media profiles were also defined. All these materials were completed in the first 5 months of the project. The files were shared by all institutions via email and the EMDESK platform. They were also made publicly available through the project’s website, as shown in the *Figure 1*.

Figure 1 – Dissemination of the brand identity on the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators website

2.1 Communication channels and activities

EMDESK

The management of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project uses EMDESK as the project management tool. This tool has been made available from the beginning of the project and in addition to its project management functions, it is used as a platform for sharing the final version of the project files (minutes, agendas, deliverables, etc) among the team members. The files are up-to-date and are made available by the responsible team whenever necessary.

Meetings

Online meetings are held regularly via MS Teams. In addition to the meetings between each WP, monthly meetings are held between the coordination team and the other five WP leaders. Every six months General Assembly and Executive Board meetings take place on site. There have already been carried out two face-to-face meetings of each, which brought together the members of the executive board and representatives of the WPs.

Meeting agendas/minutes

The meeting agendas and minutes are shared via email and archived at EMDESK.

Email

Email is an important tool in the context of communication between team members in sharing information and organizing work. The exchange of emails between teams is shared by WP1, allowing close monitoring of information and workflows. In addition to personal addresses, group/team addresses created in EMDESK are also used.

Newsletter

The inaugural newsletter issue was posted on the website in November 2023 (*Figure 2*). The second edition, released in December 2023, spotlighted the initial outcomes of the Work Package that initiated its activities earlier. These newsletters were shared between the project team via email and EMDESK and were published to the general public via the project website at <https://www.entrenovators.eu/public-files/newsletter-archive>. The launch of each edition was reinforced by the presence on social media.

Figure 2 – E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators newsletter N°1 and N°2

Additionally, in September 2023, the project was featured in the newsletters of two cluster projects from the same call: BETTER Life and EXPER. These publications provided an overview of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, along with details on its website and social media (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3 – BETTER Life project newsletter, September 2023

Figure 4 – EXPER project newsletter, September 2023

The project has also been present occasionally in institutional newsletters such as the bimonthly newsletter "Move-te" (Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7) and the monthly newsletter "Ciência no IPS" (Figure 8), both from IPS, totaling four presences in institutional newsletters.

Figure 5 – IPS Newsletter "Move-te", October 2022

Figure 6 – IPS Newsletter "Move-te", March 2023

Figure 7 – IPS Newsletter "Move-te", November 2023

INVESTIGAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO

1

UM ANO DE E³UDRES² ENT-R-E-NOVATORS

Nos passados dias 5 e 6 de outubro de 2023, os **seis países fundadores da Universidade Europeia E³UDRES²** reuniram-se na Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, na **Hungria**, para **comemorar e discutir o primeiro ano de trabalho conjunto** no âmbito do projeto **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators**. Durante estes dois dias realizaram-se a 3rd General Assembly Meeting e a 4th Executive Board Meeting. A reunião do Executive Board contou com a presença da Pró-Presidente Raquel Barreira em representação do IPS.

Este evento marca um ano de esforços colaborativos para **desenvolver estratégias conjuntas de investigação e inovação**. Entre os objetivos do projeto E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators está a **co-criação de uma estratégia e agenda comum para acelerar a**

Figure 8 – Newsletter "Ciência no IPS", November 2023

Website

The project's website is online since month five. The website includes the pages "About Ent-r-e-novators", "What we do", "E³UDRES² Alliance", "News & Events", "Public files", "Clustering" and "Contacts". The "News & Events" page is the most dynamic and the most visited one on the site and has regularly updated content (Figure 9). This page has been fed with content about E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators news, WP achievements, Institutions events, Cluster Projects news and events. Since its launch, the site has been fed with about twenty articles. Documents such as press releases, newsletters and videos are also added to the site whenever they are published.

Figure 9 – E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators website

Social media channels

The social media of the project, LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Facebook and Youtube, were created in month 6 of the project. The targets for these channels are professionals and academics (LinkedIn), the scientific and academic community and citizens interested in science (X) and the community of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators' institutions and citizens interested in science (Facebook). Since their creation, about 100 posts have been published, usually once a week (Table 1). The majority of the posts are about E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators news and events, WP goals and achievements, Institutions events, cluster projects news and events and associated scientific events. Occasionally, posts are also published on the social networks of the institutions involved in the project.

Table 1 – E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators social media posts

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - IPS Twitter	https://twitter.com/ipssetubal/status/1578036198987091969	Post about the Ent-r-e-novators Kick-off meeting	M1
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators	Creation of Twitter profile	M6
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrenovators	Creation of LinkedIn profile	M6
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/@entrenovators	Creation of YouTube channel	M6
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/entrenovators	Creation of Facebook profile	M6
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1641076980123672582	Post on Twitter about the kick off meeting at IPS	M6

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - LinkedIn	Link	Post on LinkedIn about the kick off meeting at IPS	M6
Social media - Facebook	Link	Post on Facebook about the kick off meeting at IPS	M6
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oYKUB4FLxus	Post with a video of an interview with Luís Coelho, project coordinator	M6
ViA's Social media - Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/p/CpupZbKKbV/	Post on Twitter about 2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M6
ViA's Social media - Facebook	https://www.instagram.com/p/CpupZbKKbV/	Post on LinkedIn about 2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M6
ViA's Press release - 2º GnA meeting	Link	2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M6
ViA's Press release - 2º GnA meeting	Link	2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M6
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1646834562914197504	Post on Twitter about 2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M7
Social media - LinkedIn	Link	Post on LinkedIn about 2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M7
Social media - Facebook	Link	Post on Facebook about 2nd GnA meeting in Austria	M7
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1649331024810106880	Post about the kick-off workshop meeting of WP6	M7
Social media - Facebook	Link	Post about the kick-off workshop meeting of WP6	M7
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057365243529748482	Post about the online launch of the project's website	M7
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1651594297827815425	Post about the online launch of the project's website	M7
Social media - Facebook	Link	Post about the online launch of the project's website	M7
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1656801401752760320	Post about the Major Ent-r-e-novators project's goals	M8
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062098878791045121	Post about the Major Ent-r-e-novators project's goals	M8

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/entrenovators/posts/145508395162897	Post about the Major Ent-r-e-novators project's goals	M8
Social media - Facebook	Link	Post about the first two Ent-r-e-novators surveys	M8
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1660628928426397697	Post about the first two Ent-r-e-novators surveys	M8
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7066347180801839104	Post about the first two Ent-r-e-novators surveys	M8
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7091820721391198208	Post about the new videos on Youtube	M10
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7092088006756446208	Post about Exper Workshop on Good Practices from USA	M10
Social media - Facebook	Link	E³UDRES² International Citizen Science Conference	M8
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1661734364311617548	E³UDRES² International Citizen Science Conference	M8
Social media - Facebook	Link	Post-doc applications dissemination	M9
Social media - Facebook	Link	1st International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions (ICRSR 2023)	M0
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1677054135965712384	1st International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions (ICRSR 2023)	M10
Social media - Facebook	Link	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1683955091231891459	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1683955183552720897	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d_AkOt2IUps	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y1npgSGZaMI	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Nnm2K-iEF2w	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ui_b4Oehu1l8	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Facebook	Link	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1684509256505077761	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Facebook	Link	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1684728968174280704	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Facebook	link	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M10
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1685072098316685312	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project interview	M9
Social media - Twitter	link	Ent-r-e-novators will be at the European Researchers' Night at IPS	M12
Social media - Facebook	Link	Ent-r-e-novators will be at the European Researchers' Night at IPS	M12
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7106973463898148864	Ent-r-e-novators will be at the European Researchers' Night at IPS	M12
Social media - Twitter	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1701598679558496408	1st International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions (ICRSR 2023),	M12
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=221392470907822&set=pb.100091112120433.-2207520000&type=3	1st International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions (ICRSR 2023),	M12
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7107361159673954304	1st International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions (ICRSR 2023),	M12
Social media - Twitter	(8) EUDRES Entrenovators (@entrenovators) / X (twitter.com)	Talent Management trends, challenges and pitfalls webinar	M12
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7110582435301453826	Talent Management trends, challenges and pitfalls webinar	M12
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=2229646226749113&set=a.112933668420370	Talent Management trends, challenges and pitfalls webinar	M12
Social media - Facebook MATE	-	GnA Meeting at MATE	M12

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - Facebook MATE	-	Post about the first year's results of the project	M12
Social media - Twitter	(8) EUDRES Entrenovators (@entrenovators) / X (twitter.com)	European Researchers' Night 2023	M12
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7113191671135174656	European Researchers' Night 2023	M12
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=231408119906257&set=a.112933668420370	European Researchers' Night 2023	M12
Press release MATE	-	One-year anniversary	M12
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=289673110519468&set=a.123892960430818	Facebook post about one-year anniversary	M12
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/agrargazdasag/posts/pfbid0NVkpiYyRsJUx7GEs39uTjLDnkdBYAiDSDCWpztYoaBA4rCMfGHBmAHRnhsg2BCzl	Facebook post about video testimonials	M12
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/entrenovators/posts/pfbid0QdV4oshKfNgRWbLGG86ZYB81FXJCMAWATxG8eZhaTzf3636fhQqCcl42onJUSK6l	Post about Celebrating a year of joint work on strategies in Science in Hungary	M13
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1711772259696701845	Post about Celebrating a year of joint work on strategies in Science in Hungary	M13
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7117536021906366464	Post about Celebrating a year of joint work on strategies in Science in Hungary	M13
Social media - Via's Facebook	Link	Post about Celebrating a year of joint work on strategies in Science in Hungary	M13
Social media - Youtube	(1) 2023 10 05 WP2 1 year overview - YouTube	Publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP2	M13
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=247250728321996&set=a.112933668420370	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP2	M13
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1716817664956567933	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP2	M13
Social media - LinkedIn	-	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP2	M13
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lgTF1VQv20o	Publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP3	M13
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=248357681544634&set=a.112933668420370	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP3	M13

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1717499815305637973	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP3	M13
Social media - LinkedIn	-	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP3	M13
Social media - Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A0pknvUCLs	Publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP4	M13
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=250626577984411&set=a.112933668420370	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP4	M13
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1718960947014901927	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP4	M13
Social media - LinkedIn	-	Post about the publication of a video of the Ent-r-e-novators' video series WP4	M13
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=256506634063072&set=a.112933668420370	Dissemination of the first Ent-r-e-novators' newsletter to enhance project awareness and outreach	M14
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1722920705828811083	Dissemination of the first Ent-r-e-novators' newsletter to enhance project awareness and outreach	M14
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128685137298366465	Dissemination of the first Ent-r-e-novators' newsletter to enhance project awareness and outreach	M14
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=259882593725476&set=a.112933668420370	Post for the dissemination and awareness of the publication of the "Citizen Science Chronicles" Podcast on Spotify	M14
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/172513429227895805	Post for the dissemination and awareness of the publication of the "Citizen Science Chronicles" Podcast on Spotify	M14
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130899335600320512	Post for the dissemination and awareness of the publication of the "Citizen Science Chronicles" Podcast on Spotify	M14
Social media - Facebook	(20+) Facebook	Celebrating World Science Day	M14
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133062251871129605	Celebrating World Science Day	M14
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1727297485423747312	Celebrating World Science Day	M14
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1730173934451011954	E ³ UDRES ² Ent-r-e-novators Project: WP3 - Shaping the Future of RD&I Collaboration	M14
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=267642052949530&set=a.112933668420370	E ³ UDRES ² Ent-r-e-novators Project: WP3 - Shaping the Future of RD&I Collaboration	M14

Activity	Link	Description	Month
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135940148789174272	E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Project: WP3 - Shaping the Future of RD&I Collaboration	M14
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7137851623841660929	Post about the International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions	M15
Social media - Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=270564805990588&set=a.112933668420370	Post about the International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions	M15
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1732086946535522598	Post about the International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions	M15
Social media - Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/p/C0i_gKkMyDf/	Post to get to know the project	M15
Social media - Facebook	(19) Facebook	Dissemination of the second Entrenovators' newsletter to raise Project dissemination and awareness	M15
Social media - X (Twitter)	(7) EUDRES Entrenovators (@entrenovators) / X (twitter.com)	Dissemination of the second Entrenovators' newsletter to raise Project dissemination and awareness	M15
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7140675505602584576	Dissemination of the second Entrenovators' newsletter to raise Project dissemination and awareness	M15
Social media - Facebook	(20) Facebook	Post about the Survey on the European university alliance E³UDRES²	M15
Social media - X (Twitter)	https://twitter.com/entrenovators/status/1735629160733667500/photo/1	Post about the Survey on the European university alliance E³UDRES²	M15
Social media - LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7141393595294519297	Post about the Survey on the European university alliance E³UDRES²	M15

The social media profiles, depicted from *Figure 10* to *Figure 13*, adhere closely to the brand's identity. Consistent inclusion of the logo, adherence to designated colors and typography, and the explicit reference to the financier are maintained throughout.

Figure 10 – Youtube

Figure 11 – Facebook

Figure 12 – X (Twitter)

Figure 13 – LinkedIn

Project No 101071317

Apart from its consistent presence on Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, the project extends its reach to the music streaming app Spotify with the podcast "E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Citizen Science Chronicles" (Figure 14 – Podcast "E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Citizen Science Chronicles" Figure 14). This podcast features interviews with experts in Citizen Science within the European University Alliance E³UDRES², conducted as part of the WP5 initiative. WP5 focuses on gathering and co-creating engagement models to involve researchers and citizens in assessing and inspiring their perceptions and expectations for citizen science projects. The podcast has been shared on social media platforms and on the project website.

Figure 14 – Podcast "E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Citizen Science Chronicles"

Print materials

The printed materials of the project, brochure, ID cards and roll-up (Figure 15), are available for digital or printed use from month 5 of the project. These materials have been used to accompany some of the project's attendances at events, as well as in its face-to-face meetings. Editable files of these materials have been made available to all partners by email and EMDESK. The Brochure contextualizes the project's general objectives and those of each working group and frames the E³UDRES² alliance.

Figure 15 – Print materials (roll-up, badge, and brochure)

Press releases

During the first first year and a half of implementation of the project 4 press releases were published (Figure 16). These press releases were written in English and made available on the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators website.

Figure 16 – Press releases October 2022, February, September and December 2023

In addition, the files were shared with the institutions so that they could be translated into their national languages and then distributed to local media, as exemplified in the October 2022 press release on MATE's website (Figure 17).

Figure 17 – Press release October 2022 at MATE’s website

The publication of these press releases generated occasional local media coverage, visible in the two examples by portuguese local digital news presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18 – News about the project at Setúbal media, October 2022

Beneficiary channels

The channels of each institution have been used to disseminate information about the project, especially on the websites (Figure 19 and Figure 20) and social media (Figure 21). Information management is centralized in the project management team that liaises with each person responsible for communication at each institution.

Figure 19 – ViA's Ent-r-e-novators webpage in English

Figure 20 – Ent-r-e-novators article at IPS's webpage

Figure 21 – Posts at IPS' and MATE's Social media

Video series

The first three videos of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series (9 short videos, 3 per project year) were produced in month 13 of the project. The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series aims to disseminate the project goals, activities and results. These first three videos were about the activities and results of WP2, WP3 and WP4 (Figure 22). They were published online on the project's webpage and on the YouTube channel. The information about the publication of the videos was shared internally by email and by EMDESK, and for a wider audience, researchers and the academic community of institutions, through social media (Figure 23 and Figure 24).

Figure 22 – Video series on E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators Youtube

Figure 23 – Posts at MATE’s Social media

Figure 24 – Posts at E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators’ Social media

In addition to the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series, six other videos were produced, providing insights into the project coordinator's vision and perspectives from representatives of the six hosting institutions. These videos have been widely distributed across social media platforms and featured on the project's official website. (Figure 25).

Entrenovators LC interview - VIA

Category: Video – 06 September 2023

Entrenovators LC interview - UCLL

Category: Video – 06 September 2023

Entrenovators LC interview - UTP

Category: Video – 31 August 2023

Entrenovators LC interview - IPS

Category: Video – 31 August 2023

Entrenovators coordinator interview

Category: Video – 31 March 2023

Figure 25 – Videos on E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators website

European Researchers' Night

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators was present at the European Researchers' Night event on 29 September 2023 at IPS, UTP, STPUAS and MATE. The presence of Ent-r-e-novators was established using both printed and digital materials, alongside representatives of the project. *Figure 26*, *Figure 27*, *Figure 28* and *Figure 29* illustrate the presence of the project in these institutions, as well as some interaction with the project's digital materials.

Figure 26 – European Researchers' Night at MATE

Figure 27 – European Researchers' Night at UTP

Figure 28 – European Researchers' Night at MATE

Figure 29 – European Researchers' Night at IPS

In addition to the presence of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators at the European Researchers' Night, other presentations or showcases, referred to in Table 2, took place during the first months of the project's execution. All these presences, twenty in total, that took place in several countries of the institutions involved in the project, have made it possible to raise the project's visibility and recognition both within and beyond the Alliance.

Table 2 – presentation, showcase or reference at events

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
Reference to the project in a presentation at Ostfalia University of Applied Sciences	Presentation about the project	Project dissemination and awareness	M2	IPS	Ostfalia University community
Reference to the project in the Presentation at the Digital Skills for Education & Innovation Workshop, organised by UPT	Presentation about the project	Project dissemination and awareness	M3	IPS	UTP community
Presentation about the project	Reference about the project (in person, IPS) to the Secretary of State for Higher Education as part of a visit to the IPS within the scope of the relocated Council of Ministers	Project dissemination and awareness	M6	IPS	Portuguese government
Presentation about the project	Reference about the project being presented (in person, IPS) to the Minister of Foreign Affairs as part of a visit to the IPS within the scope of the relocated Council of Ministers	Project dissemination and awareness	M6	IPS	Portuguese government
Forschungsforum der österreichischen Fachhochschulen (Research forum of the Austrian universities of applied sciences)	Presentation of E ³ UDRES ² satellite projects (including Ent-r-e-novators) by Gabriele Permoser	Project dissemination and awareness	M7	STPUAS	STPUAS community

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
UIIN Conference	Presentation of E³UDRES² satellite projects (including Ent-r-e-novators) by Gabriele Permoser	Project dissemination and awareness	M8	Budapest	Entrenovators' institutions and regions
Youth Entrepreneurship Week	Presentation of international projects at STPUAS	Project dissemination and awareness	M9,10	Vienna	STPUAS' community and region
31. #ForschungsChillOut	Presentation of international projects at STPUAS	Project dissemination and awareness	M9	STPUAS	STPUAS' community and region
Reference to the project being presented (in person, IPS) within the scope of the International IPS Week	Presentation about the project	Project dissemination and awareness	M6	IPS	Entrenovators' institutions and regions
Presentation about the project	Presentation at "Kaposvári Állattenyésztési Napok" - a national expo	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	MATE	Higher education institutions
Presentation about the project	E³UDRES² Forum 2023 (in-person, St. Polten) reference to the project in the panel "Building foundations: panel reflection on E³UDRES² Objectives, Achievements and Challenges"	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	STPUAS	E³UDRES² institutions
Presentation about the project	E³UDRES² Forum 2023 (in-person, St. Polten) reference to the project in the breakout session "Research focused on Missions & Regional Challenges"	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	STPUAS	E³UDRES² institutions
Presentation about the project	E³UDRES² Forum 2023 (in person, St. Polten) reference to the project in the workshop "Empower Ent-r-e-novators to Accelerate Future Universities"	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	STPUAS	E³UDRES² institutions
Event - European Researchers' Night 2023 at IPS	Showcase/presence of the project during the event	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	IPS	IPS community and region
Event - European Researchers' Night 2023 at UTP	Showcase/presence of the project during the event	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	UTP	UTP community and region
Event - European Researchers' Night 2023 at STPUAS	Showcase/presence of the project during the event	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	STPUAS	STPUAS community and region
Event - European Researchers' Night 2023 at Mate	Showcase/presence of the project during the event	Project dissemination and awareness	M12	MATE	MATE community and region

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
Event - 1st Institutional Science Day	Presentation about the project during the event	Project dissemination and awareness	M13	IPS	Higher education institutions
Event: Seminar Development of the Alentejo Coast: contributions to networking	Showcase/presence of the project during the event	Project dissemination and awareness	M13	Vila Nova de Santo André, Portugal	IPS community and region
Presentation to Ostfalia University of Applied Sciences	Presentation to Ostfalia University of Applied Sciences	Project dissemination and awareness	M14	IPS	Ostfalia University community
Presentation about the project	Reference about the project in the 1st International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions	Project dissemination and awareness	M15	IPS	E ³ UDRES ² researchers

2.2 Exploitation and dissemination activities

At this stage of the project, our activities have primarily focused on communication and partly on dissemination, aiming to tangibly utilize the results achieved through exploitation. In the subsequent phases of our project narrative, we plan to intentionally shift towards a more significant emphasis on dissemination and exploitation. The initial emphasis on communication serves as a precursor, setting the stage for comprehensive outreach and exploitation efforts in the latter part of the project. This strategic sequence allows us to leverage the insights, innovations and achievements cultivated during the project development journey, translating them into impactful results and tangible benefits for our stakeholders and wider communities. As we embark on this approach we will promote a path of exploitation and engagement with the results of our project. Dissemination and exploitation activities will be carried out in the second part of the project building upon the results obtained during the development of the project.

2.3 Monitoring communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

The Quality assurance and risk management plan (Deliverable D1.4) guides the project's implementation regarding the effective achievement of its objectives, having defined procedures and indicators for each WP. WP1, responsible for managing and ensuring the implementation of the project, is also responsible for ensuring the dynamization of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The "Table 11 – P4. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation" of deliverable D1.4, presents three activities included in the Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan:

- A1 Promote effective communication between partners

- A2 Promote an effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation considering the external target audiences
- A3 Organization of a science-policy conference

These activities, outlined in Table 3, excluding "A1," which has been successfully implemented, and "A3," scheduled for completion in the project's final months, have all been initiated and are currently in progress. These ongoing activities span the entire project duration, persisting until the 36th month.

Indicators 51 to 56, designed for tracking communication, dissemination, and exploration activities, encompass the monitoring of tools and actions outlined in the Project Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan. The surveillance of these activities, detailed in Table 4 to Table 9, enables the confirmation of the successful execution of all tasks, each completed on or before the specified deadline. There was a minor deviation noted in the launch of the website and the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series; however, this did not impede the project's progress or the attainment of its objectives.

Table 3 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan monitoring report

	Indicator	Description	Goal	1 st Monitoring (Oct 22 - Mar 23)	2 nd Monitoring (Apr 23 - Sept 23)	Progress Indicator	State
A1	51	Internal communication platform, EMDESK, 100% operational to be used by all partners until month 3	100%	100%	Done	
A2	52	Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan and its revisions finished on schedule	100%	100%	100%	Ongoing	
	53	Data Management plan finished, and its update finished on schedule	100%	100%	100%	Ongoing	
	54	Communication activities implemented as planned	75%	100%	Ongoing	
	55	Dissemination and exploitation activities implemented as planned	75%	100%	Ongoing	
A3	56	Conference carried out on schedule	100%	

Table 4 – # Indicator: 51 – Internal communication platform, EMDESK, 100% operational to be used by all partners until month 3

EMDESK, 100% operational	Expected date	Actual date	Difference between dates	Indicator accomplishment
EMDESK	31/12/2022	31/12/2022	0	Yes

Table 5 – # Indicator: 52 – Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan and its revisions finished on schedule

Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan	Expected date	Actual date	Difference between dates	Indicator accomplishment
Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan	31/03/2023	28/03/2023	-3	Yes
Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication report - part 1	31/12/2023			Yes
Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication report - part 2	30/09/2025			Yes

Table 6 – # Indicator: 53 – Data Management Plan finished, and its update finished on schedule

Data Management Plan finished, and its update finished on schedule	Expected date	Actual date	Difference between dates	Indicator accomplishment
Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan	31/03/2023	28/03/2023	-3	Yes
Updated Data Management plan	30/04/2024			Yes

Table 7 – # Indicator: 54 – Communication activities implemented as planned

Data Management Plan finished, and its update finished on schedule	Beginning date	Actual date	Difference between dates	Indicator accomplishment
EMDESK	31/10/2022	01/10/2022	-30	Yes
Meetings	31/10/2022	07/10/2022	-24	Yes
Meeting agendas/minutes	31/10/2022	01/10/2022	-30	Yes
Logo and Brand Book	30/11/2022	21/11/2022	-9	Yes
Project documents and presentation templates	31/12/2022	22/11/2022	-39	Yes
Emails	31/10/2022	01/10/2022	-30	Yes
Project website	31/03/2023	30/04/2023	30	
Project social media	31/03/2023	29/03/2023	-2	Yes
Print materials	30/04/2023	01/03/2023	-60	Yes
Press releases	31/10/2022	06/10/2022	-25	Yes
Beneficiaries' channels (website/social media)	31/10/2022	06/10/2022	-25	Yes
E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series	31/10/2023	15/11/2023	15	
Conference	31/03/2025			Yes
Participation in the European Researchers' Night	29/09/2023	29/09/2023	0	Yes

Table 8 – # Indicator: 55 – Dissemination and exploitation activities implemented as planned

Data Management Plan finished, and its update finished on schedule	Beginning date	Actual date	Difference between dates	Indicator accomplishment
EMDESK	31/10/2022	01/10/2022	-30	Yes
Meetings	31/10/2022	07/10/2022	-24	Yes
Meeting agendas/minutes	31/10/2022	01/10/2022	-30	Yes
Logo and Brand Book	30/11/2022	21/11/2022	-9	Yes
Project documents and presentation templates	31/12/2022	22/11/2022	-39	Yes
Emails	31/10/2022	01/10/2022	-30	Yes
Sensitive deliverables	30/11/2022			Yes
Public deliverables	31/03/2023	28/03/2022	-368	Yes
Project website	31/03/2023	30/04/2023	30	Yes
Project social media	31/03/2023	29/03/2023	-2	Yes
Print materials	30/04/2023	01/03/2023	-60	Yes
Press releases	31/10/2022	06/10/2022	-25	Yes
Beneficiaries' channels (website/social media)	31/10/2022	06/10/2022	-25	Yes
E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series	31/10/2023			Yes
Conference	31/03/2025			Yes
Participation in the European Researchers' Night	29/09/2023	29/09/2023	0	Yes
The I Living Labs for Junior Ent-r-e-novators				
Surveys				
Workshops				
Scientific Magazines				
Databases and repositories				

Table 9 – # Indicator: 56 – Conference carried out on schedule

Conference carried out on schedule	Expected date	Actual date	Difference between dates	Indicator accomplishment
Ent-r-e-novators science-policy conference	31/03/2025			

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